

**A perspective study on various molecular and in silico methods for identification of
ovarian cancer biomarkers**

Shristi Kishore and Shilpa Prasad

*Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi, Jharkhand, 834001,
India*

Email: shristi.kishore@student.amity.edu

Ovarian cancer is one of the deadliest gynaecologic cancers throughout the whole world that is associated with female reproductive system. The symptoms of this cancer remain “silent” in its early stages resulting in diagnostic delays and thus contributing to poor survival rates in various patients. The survival rates have been reported to increase if ovarian cancer is screened at its onset stages. Biomarkers play an important role in the diagnosis, prognosis, and management of ovarian cancer. Biomarker is a characteristic that is precisely measured and evaluated and then can be used as a mark of different biological processes. Researchers around the world have put tremendous efforts to identify potential biomarkers for ovarian cancer that can be used to detect the cancer at early stages and may also assist in the treatment. The advent of new technologies in the field of bioinformatics, genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics has facilitated the process for the discovery of novel biomarkers. The present review aims to discuss about well-established as well as newly discovered in silico and molecular approaches that are helpful in the identification and characterization of ovarian cancer biomarkers. The present work is done through screening of more than thirty pieces of literature available on different online databases including PubMed, Web of science, Cross Ref, and Google Scholar. Furthermore, key insights into the novel potential ovarian cancer biomarkers and their clinical utility have also been provided in this review.

Keywords: Biomarkers, Ovarian malignancy, In silico techniques, Omics-based screening, Cancer.